

INT. TV STUDIO - DAY

OFFICER SCRIPT

Our host GAVIN stands in the middle of the flashy, hi-tech studio, facing seated audience members on one side, while screens dance with various graphics behind him. Five USERS (and FAKE USERS) are arranged in a semicircle around him at the edge of a slightly raised area. The actual users occupy spaces 2 and 4 in the semicircle.

GAVIN

Welcome back, ladies and gents, to this special edition of "Hearsay". I'm Gavin Michaels. Shocking news out of London today as we learned of the death of hotel maven and society darling, Elena Armova. Did you all hear about this?

USERS (AND FAKE USERS)

Yes... terrible... couldn't believe it... (etc.)

GAVIN

Police are being very tight-lipped about this case, refusing to comment on cause of death or even if they suspect foul play. What do you think?

He turns to FAKE USER 1-

FAKE USER 1

Yeah... it would be pretty unusual for someone so young and healthy to just drop dead like that.

Gavin turns to FAKE USER 2 (in spot 3)-

GAVIN

Do you agree?

FAKE USER 2

Foul play, for sure.

GAVIN

What are your most pressing questions about this case?

FAKE USER 3

How much money did Zeller stand lose because of Armova?

GAVIN

Good question... speaks to motive. Any more?

FAKE USER 2

Why did Christine Gerard, the assistant, lie about her wrist wound? She's gotta be guilty of something.

GAVIN

We'll see if we can get any more info out of the police. ...So have you all heard about this new technology that interrogators can use? They take security footage, news recordings, personal videos... everything a person has ever recorded... and then they feed it into an artificial intelligence program that can then recreate someone's personality? Let's talk to Howard Champman.

HOWARD

It's pretty cutting edge. This would allow police to actually interview the victim herself. It would be fascinating to see

if they're planning to use the technology in this case...

GAVIN

...Thank you Howard. And now to answer all our burning questions, we have our correspondent on the scene in Mayfair, Maria Espinoza...

Gavin turns and the screen behind him switches to the street in front of Armova's apartment building, where MARIA stands holding a microphone.

MARIA

That's right, Gavin. I'm Maria Espinoza, reporter here. Police have been in and out of Miss Armova's building all day...

GAVIN

Maria, our audience wants to know what's happening with suspects Ryan Zeller and Christine Gerard. They both seem to have something to hide.

MARIA

Yes, despite the police silence around this case, rumors are flying. Ah, it looks like someone is coming out now, yes...

She moves toward the police tape by the front door, where SARGE (from Video 1) is exiting the building.

As she does so, the audience is immediately transported to the street in front of Armova's apartment, now watching the scene as if they are right there.

MARIA (CONT'D)

I'm going to see if I can speak with the officer who's just come out...

Raising her hand and shouting-

MARIA (CONT'D)

Excuse me... officer...

The Officer stops with an annoyed huff, but appears willing to be interviewed.

MARIA (CONT'D)

With whom am I speaking?

OFFICER

Officer Pearson, Metropolitan
Police Service.

MARIA

Officer, what can you tell us
about the death of Elena Armova?
Was this murder?

OFFICER

I'm afraid I can't comment on
an ongoing investigation.
You'll have to wait for the
press briefing like everyone
else...

MARIA

But Officer, our viewers have
questions...

(turning toward camera)

GAVIN

Officer, do you think Ryan
Zeller killed Armova?

The Officer pauses for a moment, choosing his words carefully.

OFFICER

I'm afraid I can't comment on anything or anyone related to this case...

MARIA

Is Zeller in custody?

Officer turns and walks toward his car as Maria follows, doggedly.

OFFICER

I'm sorry, no comment.

MARIA

...What about Christine Gerard, Miss Armova's assistant?

Officer stops for a moment.

MARIA (CONT'D)

Miss Gerard visited the victim the night of the murder and has an unexplained injury, what can you tell us about that?

Officer turns, an accusatory eye for the persistent reporter.

OFFICER

Where did you get your information?

MARIA

Miss Gerard is rarely far from Miss Armova's side. Her absence from the public eye over the last twenty-four hours is suspect, to say the least. Wouldn't you agree?

OFFICER

I am unable to comment at this time.

MARIA

Will the police be employing their controversial new AI technology in this case? Will you be interviewing Armova herself?

Officer turns back toward her, thoughtful for a moment.

OFFICER

Since Miss Armova was such a public figure, that is an option.

(MORE)

OFFICER (CONT'D)

I'm afraid I can't say any more than that. Now if you'll excuse me...

Officer tips his hat and exits the scene. Maria turns back to the camera with a shrug.

MARIA

There you have it, Gavin. Police are refusing to comment on the two individuals with the closest ties to Armova. However, Officer Pearson did confirm that AI technology may be used to help solve this crime.

Our world once again becomes the TV studio, with Maria and the street scene on a screen behind the hosts.

GAVIN

Very interesting, Maria, thank you.

He turns back to the Users.

GAVIN (CONT'D)

Well, audience, was it the boyfriend, Zeller? The assistant, Gerard? Was it suicide? A botched robbery? A drug overdose? What do you think?

FAKE USER 2

It would be nice to get in that apartment and have a look around.

GAVIN

Yes, and I bet you'd love to hear from Armova herself, wouldn't you? That might answer a few questions. Well, ladies and gents, that's our program for today. Be sure to tune in next time to see me and for more on this story, and all the news you just can't stop talking about, on the next edition of... "Hearsay".

I'm Gavin Michaels...

Closing titles swirl, music fades as the studio goes dark.

THE END

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SERGEANT SCRIPT

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MARIA (CONT'D)

Excuse me... officer...

The Sarge stops with an annoyed huff, but appears willing
to be interviewed.

MARIA (CONT'D)

With whom am I speaking?

SARGE

Sergeant Hoffstetler, Metropolitan
Police Service.

MARIA

Sergeant, what can you tell us
about the death of Elena Armova?
Was this murder?

SARGE

I'm afraid I can't comment on
an ongoing investigation.
You'll have to wait for the
press briefing like everyone
else...

MARIA

But Sergeant, our viewers have
questions...

(turning toward camera)

GAVIN

Sergeant, do you think Ryan
Zeller killed Armova?

The Sarge pauses for a moment, choosing his words carefully.

SARGE

I'm afraid I can't comment on anything or anyone related to this case...

MARIA

Is Zeller in custody?

Sarge turns and walks toward his car as Maria follows, doggedly.

SARGE

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SARGE

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SARGE

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(MORE)

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